

SECTIONAL MEETINGS

Details of technical meetings follow. See map for building locations. Business meetings are scheduled for each section. An important item of business is the election of officers.

10:45 VARIATION OF COUNTS OF BIRDS IN A NORTHEASTERN OHIO WOODS. Cynthia Hafner and David Waller. Kent State University, Department of Biological Sciences, Kent, Ohio 44242.

Season- or habitat-related variability in bird populations can affect patterns revealed by restricted surveys of an area. If single surveys are to be effective indicators of birds present, then little variation should be present among spatial or temporal survey points. Bird populations of two adjacent sections of deciduous forest in Ashtabula County, Ohio were repeatedly observed over a two-month period. Three transect lines were established 580 feet apart, and stations were selected along these lines every 400 feet. At each stop, all individual birds observed by sight or sound for an eight minute interval were identified to species, counted, and recorded. Data for selected species were tested for randomness of occurrence among stations and among dates. Common species of birds that inhabit the floor of the woods (such as Ovenbirds and Wood Thrushes) did not occur randomly in the censuses, while common arboreal species (such as Eastern Wood Pewees and Red-eyed Vireos) were more random in their dispersion and seasonal occurrence. Uncommon species of both arboreal birds (such as Yellow-throated Vireos) and floor birds (such as Veerys) tended to vary more among dates than among stations. With these censusing methods, counts for species selected for analysis did not show lower variability among stations or among dates than would be expected for either random or aggregated occurrence of individuals.

R. ECOLOGY

SECOND MORNING SESSION, SATURDAY, APRIL 23, 1983

LIFE SCIENCES BUILDING, ROOM 334

R. PETER RICHARDS, PRESIDING

8:30 THE EFFECTS OF ATRAZINE AND METOLACHLOR ON THE VEGETATIVE GROWTH OF LEMNA MINOR L. Nancy Palmstrom and Kenneth A. Krieger. Heidelberg College. Tiffin, Ohio 44883.

The effects on the vegetative growth of Lemna minor L. by atrazine and metolachlor, both separately and in combination, were studied. Dose-response studies were used to determine the inhibitory effects of these pesticides on L. minor. The growth was measured as the addition of leaves (thalli) and buds to the plants. The plants were maintained at 25 °C under continuous illumination throughout the investigation using a growth chamber to control environmental conditions.

Plants treated with 10, 100, and 200 ug/l atrazine for a 92 hour period experienced 11.3, 34.1, and 66.9 percent inhibition, respectively, as compared with controls. Similarly metolachlor caused 12.2, 54.2, and 61.0 percent inhibition after 146 hours at concentrations of 10, 100, and 200 ug/l as compared with controls. When the pesticides were used in combination, at equal concentrations totalling 10, 100, and 200 ug/l of herbicide, similar percent inhibition levels resulted. There appeared to be no enhancement effects when the pesticides were used in combination. The results indicate that atrazine and metolachlor, used individually or in combination, significantly inhibited the vegetative growth of L. minor.

8:45 PESTICIDE CONCENTRATIONS IN SANDUSKY BAY AND THE LOWER SANDUSKY RIVER FOLLOWING A SPRING STORM. R. Peter Richards, Water Quality Laboratory, Heidelberg College, Tiffin, Ohio 44883.

In the rivers of northwestern Ohio, many non-point derived pollutants reach maximum concentrations in runoff following storms in spring and early summer. This pattern also characterizes many agricultural herbicides and insecticides. Concentrations of three pesticides (Atrazine, Alachlor, Metolachlor) measured during May and June 1982 exceeded 40 ug/l in the upper Sandusky River basin (Melmore, Ohio), and exceeded 15 ug/l in the lower reached of the river (Freemont, Ohio) and in the upper portion of Sandusky Bay. By comparison, 5 ug/l is often taken as a concentration sufficient to inhibit photosynthesis in algae. In the bay, pesticides concentrations are well correlated with nitrate + nitrite, indicating that the pesticides are dissolved in the water, rather than adsorbed to suspended sediments.

9:00 THE TRANSFER OF PHOSPHATE FROM HUMIC SUBSTANCES TO BIOTA IN AN ACID BOG LAKE. James B. Cotner, Jr. and Robert T. Heath, Department of Biological Sciences, Kent State University, Kent, OH 44242.

Aquatic humic substances can release orthophosphate on irradiation with ultraviolet (UV) light. Since UV light is rapidly attenuated in brown water lakes, the